

Unequal Paths to Nature: Barriers to Greenspace Access in West Yorkshire

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Summary

Equitable access to greenspace is vital for physical and mental wellbeing of people, communities, and cities, yet a range of physical, social, and cultural barriers restrict access for many. This case study uses original data in Leeds and Bradford to model how barriers to greenspace manifest across people and place. Results of statistical tests and OLS modelling reveal how the number of barriers differs across demographic groups, with notable effects across gender, ethnicity, ability, and deprivation.

This emphasises the need to explore individual, intersectional experiences of barriers, in order to remove these obstacles and improve accessibility for all.

KEYWORDS: greenspace, access, inequality, barriers, intersectionality

1. Introduction

The spatial distribution of accessible services is a crucial indicator of urban equality. One service is public greenspace, which offers multi-faceted benefits to individuals, communities, and the environment. These include offering naturally restorative locations that facilitate healthy activities such as socialising and physical activity, and reducing urban hazards such as air pollution, flooding, and the heat island effect (Hartig et al., 2014).

While global policies, such as Sustainable Development Goal 11, aim for everyone to “have good access to greenspace” (UN, 2015), research consistently identifies socioeconomic and demographic inequalities, disproportionately affecting women, ethnic minorities, older adults, disabled people, children and young people, and low-income communities (Williams et al., 2020). These groups often face greater barriers to accessing greenspaces, which correlates with poorer physical and mental health outcomes (Gianfredi et al., 2021). Barriers may be physical; for example, those of lower socioeconomic status have poorer quality and quantity of neighbourhood greenspace provision than more privileged communities, while older and less mobile individuals commonly face physical obstructions (Gray et al., 2025). Social experiences also matter. Women are three times more likely than men to feel unsafe in parks during the daytime, while ethnic minorities often report feeling excluded or unsafe either within or navigating to their park (ONS, 2022a).

Yet, an overwhelming majority of previously small-scale, qualitative studies, have contributed to a gap in understanding around intersectional experiences of barriers to interacting with nature, and thus how they may be addressed (Gray et al., 2025). Crucially, these barriers must be conceptualised holistically, considering the physical, social, cultural, and spatial factors that exacerbate exclusion.

1.1. Research Questions

1. How do physical, social, and cultural barriers to greenspace vary across Leeds and Bradford?
2. Which personal and environmental characteristics relate to higher numbers of barriers to greenspace access?

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2. Methods

2.1 Data

This study covers Leeds and Bradford, two diverse cities in West Yorkshire (**Figure 1**). While income in both cities falls below the national average, Leeds has lower levels of ethnic minorities (20.0%) compared to Bradford, one of the most socially and ethnically diverse areas of England, where one third of residents are South Asian (ONS, 2022b).

Figure 1 Study area of Bradford and Leeds, West Yorkshire

We conducted the Leeds and Bradford Access to Parks and Green Spaces Survey between April and June 2025, co-developed with both cities' councils, collecting data on: respondents' postcodes, most used park, and visiting patterns, barriers and priorities for parks, demographic, and health characteristics. Barriers included multiple items categorised under the themes of: accessibility and transportation, facilities and maintenance, safety and comfort, social and environmental factors, activities and events, and personal factors. The questionnaire was distributed via deprivation-stratified and randomised mail outs, online via mailing lists, social media, and targeted ads (demographic and spatial), local media, and in person. We received 2,682 valid responses, 805 in Bradford and 1,877 in Leeds.

Postcodes allowed us to geo-locate respondents by postcode centroid using Ordnance Survey (OS) Code-Point (OS, 2025a), and calculate and travel distance to their main park. Public greenspace shape files were retrieved from OS Open Greenspace layer (OS, 2025b). By linking the postcodes to LSOA (Lower Super Output Area) (ONS, 2024), we added deprivation, measured by the English Index of Multiple Deprivation 2025 (MHCLG, 2025). To map spatial patterns in the number and types of barriers experienced, individual barriers were aggregated to LSOA by mean.

2.2 Analysis

Exploratory analysis allowed us to investigate the spatial and intersectional distribution of numbers of barriers to accessing greenspace. Choropleths were used to visually inspect how the number of barriers varied across both cities. This was compared statistically and visually with IMD data, using Pearson's correlation tests. Unequal variance t-tests were used to model whether the numbers of barriers differed significantly between cities.

To identify which social groups face the highest barriers to greenspace access, Kruskal-Wallis tests were applied to model differences between several different demographic groups (age, gender, ethnicity, and disability).

Finally, to investigate the risk factors for experiencing higher barriers to greenspace, Ordinary Least Squares linear regression models were used to predict the number of reported barriers from demographic and individual factors, as well as local-area deprivation. This research is ongoing, with

potential to employ Geographically Weighted Regression (GWR) to identify how relationships with greenspace barriers vary across space. Investigations into intersectional experiences and types of barriers continue.

3. Results

3.1 Statistical Analysis

Of 2,682 respondents, most people were aged 35-64 (55.6%), and White British (73.9%), with 7.5% of the respondents South Asian. There were twice as many females as males in the sample (61.0 vs 30.6%), with 2.2% identifying as non-binary/other. Just over a third (35.6%) reported a disability or long-term health condition (hereafter termed ‘disability’).

At population level, the average number of barriers to greenspace was 5.22, and was significantly higher in Bradford (5.93) than Leeds (4.99) ($t = -6.034$, $p < 0.001$). Choropleths (**Figure 2**) visualise this inequality. Although some areas of non-response are visibly missing, higher levels of deprivation (lower IMD) are observed in urban areas. Pearson correlation tests confirmed a relationship with numbers of barriers, with a statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) coefficient of 0.207, indicating a weak, positive association.

Figure 2 Barriers and deprivation across the study area

Significant differences were observed for the number of barriers experienced by various demographic groups. Younger people reported higher barriers, with 17–34-year-olds reporting an average of 6.08-6.22 barriers, compared to 4.50-4.99 for the over-50s; Kruskal-Wallis tests confirmed statistical significance, ($\chi^2(5) = 91.29$, $p < .001$). Gender differences were also pronounced $\chi^2(2) = 17.51$, $p < .001$; women reported almost 10% more barriers than men (5.42 vs 4.97), while non-binary/other-gendered individuals reported 6.54. Barriers were significantly higher among Asian populations than any other Ethnic group, with an average of 7.59 for South Asians, compared to 4.94 for White British people ($\chi^2(7) = 106.77$, $p < .001$). Disabled people had significantly higher barriers (6.22) than average, a difference most pronounced for those who said this affected them ‘a lot’ (7.65) (for disability, $t = 10.22$, $p < 0.001$).

3.2 Predicting Barriers

After comparing pair-wise correlations between each of these factors, we constructed an OLS regression model, with results shown in **Table 1**. The R^2 value indicated moderate fit (0.391), with independent variables explaining 39% of the variation in the number of barriers. The most pronounced results showed that Gender (female or non-binary), Asian Ethnicity, Disability, and Deprivation were the strongest significant predictors of higher numbers of barriers. Interestingly, the number of reported barriers decreased with Age, although only the coefficient for Over 65s (-0.872) was significant at the 5% level.

Table 1 OLS Regression Results (* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.001$)

Variable	Value	<i>B</i>
Age	<i>17-24, ref</i>	
	25-34	0.230
	35-49	-0.142
	50-64	-0.491
	Over 65	-0.872*
Gender	<i>Male, ref</i>	
	Female	0.348*
	Non-binary/other	1.28*
Ethnicity	<i>White British, ref</i>	
	White, Other	0.521
	South Asian	2.329**
	Asian, Other	2.108**
	Black	.353
	Mixed	0.231
Disability	Other	0.518
		1.603**
IMD		-0.00005**

4. Discussion

Initial findings show both spatial and demographic inequalities in barriers to greenspace access. The number of barriers was positively and significantly associated with deprivation, implying, in combination with literature, potential quality issues or that social barriers increasing in less affluent areas. Barriers were higher for women and non-binary people, Asians, and those with a disability; these could be cultural and social, such as lack of appropriate facilities or experiences of exclusion and lack of safety for certain groups, or physical such as reduced accessibility. The analysis is currently exploring these differences statistically by modelling associations with the different themes of barriers.

Interestingly, barriers were inversely associated with Age, albeit with limited statistical significance. With older age often comes mobility challenges, so this may suggest additional cultural or social barriers affecting younger age groups, for example safety or accommodation concerns, which we are investigating in ongoing analyses of the types of barriers and other experiences, such as reports of park condition and priorities for the future. Exploring how the numbers and types of reported barriers vary both spatially and demographically has so far highlighted how greenspace accessibility reaches beyond our traditional understanding of physical access, impacting social, cultural, and personal dimensions, emphasising the importance of individual experiences.

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Biographies

Victoria Houlden is an Associate Professor in Urban Data Science in the School of Geography, University of Leeds. She aims to understand the ways in which spaces and places embody inequalities, and the social structures influencing how people relate to their environment. Her current projects focus on greenspace access.

Jennie Gray is an ECR, working as a Research Fellow at the University of Leeds. She is interested in all facets of neighbourhood research, the sociodemographic processes cultivating changes, the spatiotemporal properties of those changes, and finally the human consequences of them, notably socio-spatial inequalities and their impacts on accessibility.

Anna Barker is an Associate Professor in Criminology & Criminal Justice in the School of Law, University of Leeds. Her research focuses on making public spaces feel safer and more inclusive, particularly for women and girls. She currently leads the policy-focussed *Safer Parks: Improving Access for Women and Girls* programme.